

1 **Ep300 and Ep400 in IBD.**

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7 We used transcriptomics for systems biologic discovery of factors important for IBD pathogenesis. We report here silencing of the transcriptional complexes *Ep300* and *Ep400* in the whole blood in humans with the inflammatory bowel disease Ulcerative Colitis.

8 Citations

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